

Deliverable report for

Sustainable Energy Harvesting Systems Based on Innovative Mine Waste Recycling

Project 101058632

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2 ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

Acronym	Description
EU	European Union
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
KoM	Kick-off Meeting

3 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The present **deliverable** fulfils the requirements of demonstrating the achievement of the following **objectives**:

- Creation of a graphical identity for the project: it was obtained by developing a branding set of colours, the logo, and a guideline for preparing the various project documents and materials, both for public and internal use, and to report to the EU.
- Creation of the project website: the domain www.START-HEproject.com was bought, a dedicated server installed, the basic pages for the website have been created according to the project branding, and some information about the project is already available, plus a contact tool and a tool to register for the project's mailing list. Also a second domain was bought (www.HE-START.eu) and automatically redirected to the main address.
- Creation of other online tools:
 - a LinkedIn page (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/start-he-project/>)
 - a YouTube channel (<https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCHVjEhpVz9uaEgzlCj2InPA>)
 - a Twitter account (https://twitter.com/START_Heproject)
 - a Twitch account (https://www.twitch.tv/start_he_project)
 - a SlideShare account (<https://es.slideshare.net/StartProject/>)

4 INTRODUCTION

In the original proposal, the START consortium indicated the following information about the use of **Project Graphical Identity** for Dissemination and Communication:

Tool:	Project Graphical Identity
Purpose:	A Graphical Identity for the START project (logo and general branding colour schemes, for the website, the social media, mail signatures for partners, and all other uses) will be developed in the first months.
Audience:	All groups
Due:	M02
Quantified targets:	-

As explained, the graphical identity is the base material to be used then in all communication about the project, starting from the website but including social media, documents, E-mails, and other internal and external communication tools.

4.1 SIMILARLY NAMED WEBSITES/PROJECTS

To develop the identity, it was at first important to identify possible collisions with initiatives bearing the same or similar name, and in particular with projects with similar scope, if any.

Short searches on Google were run, in order to identify possible conflicts in terms of branding and content, as the main goal of the branding is to be recognizable and distinguished from non-related projects, companies or initiatives.

We carried on 3 searches with the following exact keywords:

- “START”
- “START project”
- “START EU project”

In the following tables, only the relevant results in the first results page have been listed.

Table 1: Google search (1st page): “START”.

Description	Link	Logo
START International, Inc. is a registered non-profit organization founded in 1992 to strengthen capacities for global environmental change science in Africa and Asia that addresses critical sustainability challenges.	https://start.org/	
Start_ is an Argentinian retail supplier of electronic appliances.	https://www.start.com.ar/	
START is a Russian video streaming service.	https://start.ru	

Table 1 (continued).

Description	Link	Logo
The National Consortium for the Study of Terrorism and Responses to Terrorism, better known as START, is a Department of Homeland Security Emeritus Center of Excellence headquartered at the University of Maryland comprised of an international network of scholars committed to the scientific study of the causes and human consequences of terrorism in the United States and around the world.	https://www.start.umd.edu/	

Table 2: Google search (1st page): "START project".

Description	Link	Logo
START Project is an educational program implemented by Socialinnov at the Serafio City of Athens , that functions as an educational hub on skills of the digital era	https://www.startproject.gr/en/home/	
The START Project (Grand Valley State University, Michigan) support students with Autism Spectrum Disorder.	https://www.gvsu.edu/autismcenter/	

Table 3: Google search (1st page): "START EU project".

Description	Link	Logo
S+T+ARTS (Innovation at the nexus of Science, Technology and the Arts) has received funding from the European Commission's Directorate-General for Communications Networks, Content and Technology	https://starts.eu/	
Start the change! is a project co-funded by the European Commission aimed to raise European citizens' awareness of the importance of a joint effort to contribute to ending poverty, protecting the planet and ensuring peace and prosperity for all.	https://www.startthechange.eu/	
START EASY is an initiative promoted by the Government of Catalonia in cooperation with national, regional & local authorities as well as other stakeholders from all corners of Europe (BE, ES, FR, IT, LT, LV, PL), to enable an environment for business to start easy & quickly.	https://projects2014-2020.interregeurope.eu/starteasy/	
Start at Best contributes to the development of a European-led new wave of workplace innovation among SMEs.	https://startatbest.eu/	
With the RE-START project, partners from Spain, Greece, Cyprus, Iceland, Bulgaria and Poland aim to develop a very helpful online tool to support women – after staying at home – to re-enter the labour market	https://www.re-start-p	

Table 3 (continued).

Description	Link	Logo
Funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme, BlockStart is a pan-European DLT/ blockchain partnership programme.	https://www.blockstart.eu/	

An important piece of information obtained from this is that in the most visible results no project concerning materials, recycling and sustainability, is included. So, provided it is somewhat clear in the website name and of course in its home page that START is a project, there should be no big confusion. In other words, it is not likely that someone looking for a project on the same topic could end up in the wrong website, or vice versa land on the START project website.

4.2 BRANDING COLOURS AND LOGO

The project has a strong environmental focus, both because it intends to recycle mine waste to obtain input materials for the fabrication of thermoelectric devices, and because these devices will be used to harvest otherwise wasted heat from thermal processes, making them more energy efficient. So, we decided, before any other colours, to put **green** in our project logo to emphasize its **sustainability**.

Then two other colours were added. The **grey** symbolises the **world of mining**, and the **colour of the powders** that will constitute the thermoelectric material; while the **red** symbolises the **heat** to be harvested through the process.

Figure 1: Basic colour composition for the START Project branding.

Finally, the **logo** (Figure 2) is made up of two parts. **One part** is the symbol, the **red and green cycle** that represents the **movement** and the **sustainability** cycle of our project, and the **second part** is the **name of the project**. For the latter, a modern font was chosen, to symbolize the future. The font logo is Quantum, and the grey basic colour should be used. This is not a font that can be used normally in text, as it is inherently bold and capitalised, and is not commonly available in Microsoft Word or PowerPoint.

Figure 2: Final logo selected.

Other symbols had been imagined complementing the logo, for instance arrows, that could symbolise the conversion of heat and wastes into new energy and heat transfer, dots, also linked to powders, and a triangular icon resembling a “start” button and at the same time a cycle. These symbols were drafted in some other versions of the logo, but the final decision, taken during the General Assembly of the project held in conjunction with the KoM of Lisbon (20-21 June 2022), was to simplify the logo into only one symbol (the red-green cycle) and the “START” text. Examples of the other logos imagined are visible in Figure 3.

Another version of the logo has been prepared for some social media accounts, where a squarer logo fits better the space available for branding (Figure 4).

Further versions may be used, for instance a “negative”, white on coloured background, when a dark or anyway coloured background is foreseen, if the background cannot be changed (e.g., for inclusion in third party graphics).

It is also possible to use the cycle symbol as an animated symbol, by letting it rotate, to make the logo more dynamic where the support allows (e.g., on the website).

1	2	3
4	5	6
7	8	9
10	11	12
13	14	

Figure 3: Logos that were not selected (the bottom left version (13) was chosen as a provisional logo, but then abandoned for the final logo of Figure 2).

Figure 4: Second version of the final logo, to be used on some social media where a square logo, or anyway a logo with a different aspect ratio is requested.

4.3 BRANDING GUIDELINES

4.3.1 Graphic elements

As a branding guideline in all our communication we will “play” with the shapes inspired by the lines at the left and right of Figure 5, to obtain for instance the graphic elements shown in the centre in the same picture. Other graphic elements that can be used are shown in Figure 6.

Figure 5: Graphic elements to be used while branding documents for the project.

Figure 6: Other graphic elements to be used while branding documents for the project.

4.3.2 Font Specifications

Fonts to use are specified in the Word template (see 4.3.4).

4.3.3 Presentation template

Based on the provisional branding and logo selected before the KoM, a PowerPoint pptx template was prepared so that the presentations in the meeting could be branded consistently. An empty slide of this provisional version is visible in Figure 7.

Figure 7: Provisional START internal presentation template (June 2022, used in the KoM).

After the KoM and the selection of a slightly different logo by the Consortium, the template has been reworked to an official format as visible in Figure 8.

Figure 8: START internal presentation template (July 2022, updated after selection of logo in the KoM).

4.3.4 Word template

A Word template has been produced to assist in maintaining a constant style throughout the project in documents produced.

Note that although the preferred font would be Open Sans, the unavailability of this font in many applications, namely in Microsoft Office ones, advised to switch to Arial as font family. So, titles and body text and all other styles are based on different declinations (size, colour, bold, italic, etc.) of the Arial font. Where used, colours are the START grey, green and red. An image of the Word template is shown in Figure 9.

Figure 9: START Word template (July 2022).

4.3.5 Mail signature

All partners can add a reference to the project website in their E-Mail signatures. This could be in the basic form as shown in Figure 10, but it could also be updated during the project to advertise for special events (seminars, webinars, etc.) organised by START.

Figure 10: Basic START E-Mail signature.

5 PROJECT WEBSITE

In the original proposal, the START consortium indicated the following information about the use of a **project website** for Dissemination and Communication:

Tool:	Project Website
Purpose:	Main channel for information and major tool for the visibility of the START activities. Updated frequently, with a blend of status, push and active content including: project overview; public documents; agenda; articles and news; multimedia. Individuals can also use the website to sign up to the newsletter and social media channels.
Audience:	All groups
Due:	M02 onwards
Quantified targets:	Visitors: 2000 in year 1 rising to at least 4000 in year 4

The website is rather obviously central in the strategy for dissemination and communication. It is the main channel where project news and info will be placed as soon as they are available. It will allow interested readers to join the community to receive newsletters and other communications.

5.1 WEBSITE DOMAIN

The **domain name** chosen for the project website is the following:

<http://www.START-HEproject.com>

The domain was chosen to refer to the Horizon Europe program, in order to distinguish this project from similar ones of the past. The website is hosted in its own server in Clermont Ferrand with the company O2 Switch. Another domain was bought, in order to cover searches with different keywords: www.HE-START.eu. This address is automatically redirected to the main address.

5.2 WEBSITE STRUCTURE AND FEATURES

5.2.1 Home

The **website structure** is basically as follows: there is a “**Home**” page (Figure 11) with basic information, containing a cover image (the photo of the group from the KoM, for the moment) and links to internal pages and documents. The other pages, for the moment only on the same level, first level in the menu, that can be accessed via the menu bar at the top, are described in the following subchapters.

At the centre of the “Home” page, some chapters can be discovered by clicking, and contain information on the approach, the scope, and the expected impact of the START project. Below, the consortium is presented in a rolling ribbon (with clickable logos that lead to the partners’ websites). Finally, a link to the “**Subscribe**” page is given, for all who would like to make synergies with the project’s activities.

In this page widgets containing the feeds of the START social media will be available (for the moment, only Twitter is visible).

START Home The Project Documents News Multimedia Consortium CONTACT

Sustainable energy harvesting systems based on innovative mine waste recycling

A Horizon Europe project

START PROJECT OBJECTIVE

START project's primary objective is to build an innovation ecosystem in the European Union (EU) related to the development of sustainable and economically viable tellurium-free thermoelectric (TE) waste heat harvesting systems, to be applied in heavy industry, maritime industry and also as primary power source for off-grid sensors and IoT devices.

HOW TO ACHIEVE

IMPACT OF START

START PROJECT ORGANISATION

Read more in the other website pages and subscribe to our newsletter and social media channels!

START CONCEPT

Mine waste

Substrate mineral: knowledge and know-how for TE supply chain (MPT)

TEF: enabling power technology and use of waste (MPT)

Advanced characterisation (MPT)

RECOVERY AND REUSE OF MINE WASTE

THERMAL PROCESSING

DEVICE

VALIDATION

SCALE UP

Technology demonstration and commercialisation (DRL)

T-Block: Jigs, simulation, production and characterisation (MPT)

Consortium

The START project aggregates 13 organisations, from 10 EU member states and 3 associated countries, including 6 research organisations with strong background and knowledge in geo, materials science and renewables energies, 7 SMEs companies that guarantee the entire supply chain, from production, exploitation and ecological footprint assessment, and 2 non-profit international associations with a consolidated network of partners and stakeholders.

RGS MBN LNEG

Discover The Future

Our team is ready to discuss with you possible collaborations and synergies to achieve your and our goals

CONTACT US

Tweets by @START_Europe

START - HIG project

We have recently began our journey for the START (Sustainable Energy Harvesting Systems Based on Innovative Mine Waste Recycling) project with a meeting in Lisbon.

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Figure 11: Screenshot of page “Home” of the START website.

5.2.2 The Project

A general description of the rationale of the project is given in “**The Project**” page (Figure 12). It is explained how START fits with the European Green Deal and the Circular Economy Action Plan. Two links will bring to the “**Documents**” page for more information, and to the “**Subscribe**” page, respectively.

START Home The Project Documents News Multimedia Consortium CONTACT

Climate change is one of the greatest challenges

Climate change is one of the greatest challenges faced by humankind. Fighting global warming is critically dependent on the rapid implementation of a green transition to which the European Union is fully committed through the **European Green Deal**. Climate action is at the heart of this ambitious package of measures, which are heavily reliant on European supply of raw materials and on the circular feed of supply chains in strategic industry.

The START project is totally aligned with the Green Deal

The START project is totally aligned with the Green Deal objectives as it proposes a **unique technological solution**, well beyond the state of the art: collect waste sulphides of the tetrahedrite series ((Cu,Fe)12Sb4S13) from deactivated mine dumps/tailing and current mining waste flows within EU to produce optimized p-type **thermoelements** for common thermoelectric (TE) generators able to **harvest waste heat**. This concept represents a major opportunity to increase resource productivity and to decrease resource dependence and waste in line with the new **Circular Economy Action Plan**.

Project duration

Project duration: 4 years
Start: 1st June 2022
Project budget: 9.2 M€, co-funded by Horizon Europe

DOCUMENTS LET'S WORK TOGETHER

Tweets by @START_HEproject

START - HE project @START_HEproject
We have recently began our journey for the START (Sustainable Energy Harvesting Systems Based on Innovative Mine Waste Recycling) project with a meeting in Lisbon!

7 Jul 2022

Embed View on Twitter

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Twitter LinkedIn YouTube

Figure 12: Screenshot of page “The Project” of the START website.

5.2.3 Documents

This “**Documents**” page (Figure 13) will collect useful information, in particular scientific information, either freely available before the project or produced during the project. Some material will be hosted on SlideShare and then linked here. Social media posts will be used to invite people to this page and consult the relevant documents, some of which may be subjected to subscription for viewing.

There is one document now available for free downloading: it is about “Green Energy Harvesting” and is a state-of-the-art informative paper in pdf format.

Figure 13: Screenshot of page “Documents” of the START website.

5.2.4 News

Any news about the project activities that can be interesting for the public will be given in the “**News**” page (Figure 14). The articles will be also shared on social media like Twitter and LinkedIn.

Figure 14: Screenshot of page “News” of the START website.

There is only one piece of news visible, based on the description of the KoM held in Lisbon on 20-21 June 2022. In Figure 15 a screenshot of this item is visible.

START PROJECT | Home | The Project | Documents | News | Multimedia | Consortium | **CONTACT**

We STARTed! - (July 2022)

LNEG hosted the Kick-Off Meeting

We are very proud to announce the official beginning of the START project, which took place on June 1st, 2022, with the Kick-Off Meeting held on June 20 and 21 in LNEG (START's coordinator) in its premises in Lisbon, Portugal.

START, which stands for "Sustainable Energy Harvesting Systems Based on Innovative Mine Waste Recycling", with the concept of transforming mining waste into materials for use in fuel recovery, will create a sustainable supply chain and a corresponding business innovation ecosystem for zellurium free electrometric green energy harvesting products based on secondary raw materials responsibly sourced from within the European Union (EU).

START is an innovation action project supported by the EU and its Horizon Europe programme (101058632-CL4-2021-RESILIENCE-01-01).

The Consortium comprises 15 multidisciplinary institutions with large experience in international innovation projects:

- Laboratório Nacional de Energia e Geologia (LNEG) - Coordinator
- 3 Diferentes - Engenharia, Inovação e Ambiente (Lda) (PT)
- Association De Services De Géologie Y Minerie Iberomericanae (ASMI) (ES)
- Bundesanstalt Für Geowissenschaften Und Rohstoffe (BGR) (DE)
- European Powder Metallurgy Association AISBL (BE)
- Gen Core Sp. Z. o.o. (PL)
- Geo Umweltwosscher GmbH (Austria)
- Geologische Bundesanstalt (Austria)
- La Palma Research Centre SL (ES)
- MBN Nanomaterials Spa (IT)
- RDS Development BV (NL)
- Statby (Ecologicaly Ustav Dronyzv stura) (SK)
- Sincel AS (NO)
- TEGnology ApS (DK)
- Agencia Estatal Consejo Superior De Investigaciones Científicas (CSIC) (ES)

The START project has a total duration of 48 months, and 919441.25 € of total eligible costs. 47 delegates from all 15 consortium partners were present at the Kick-Off Meeting; during the session on Monday 20th June the EU Project Officer joined and could follow a thorough presentation about the project and its foreseen activities, results, and impact. First meetings of the General Assembly and of the Executive Committee took also place, and on 21st June a more operative meeting on the upcoming activities concluded the event. Some important decisions were taken and the activities of the first months were outlined.

The participants also enjoyed a consortium dinner on Monday night, that helped in making acquaintance with the other partners.

More details on the project approach and its endeavours will of course be published in this website soon. Go to the "Subscribe" page in this website to be in our mailing list and be kept informed about project activities and events!

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Figure 15: Screenshot of the news about the KoM on the START website.

5.2.5 Multimedia

In the “**Multimedia**” page (Figure 16), all multimedia files produced will be either embedded (preferable) or linked, from YouTube and Twitch.

Also, all links to the START social media accounts are given at the bottom of the page, with an encouragement to follow them.

Figure 16: Screenshot of page “Multimedia” of the START website.

5.2.6 Consortium

In the “**Consortium**” page, a European map with the consortium partners is presented (Figure 17). Now a static map is given, but in the next version the reader will be able to click on partners logos and reach their websites for details.

To compensate this temporarily missing feature, a full list of the partners with all their (clickable) websites is given below the static map.

START PROJECT | New | Edit Page | Edit Live | Hi, Bruno Vicenz | CONTACT

Home | The Project | Documents | News | Multimedia | Consortium | CONTACT

SINTEF
TEGNOLOGY
RGS DEVELOPMENT
BGR
EPMA
ASGMI
LNEG
3drivers
LPRC LA PALMA RESEARCH CENTRE
MBN nanomaterials
GeniCore
Geologische Bundesanstalt
G

Laboratorio Nacional de Energia e Geologia I.P. (PT) – Coordinator	https://www.lneg.pt/
3 Drivers – Engenharia, Inovação E Ambiente Lda (PT)	https://www.3drivers.pt/
Asociacion De Servicios De Geologia Y Minería Iberoamericanos (ES)	https://asgmi.org/
Bundesanstalt Für Geowissenschaften Und Rohstoffe (DE)	https://www.bgr.bund.de/
European Powder Metallurgy Association AISBL (BE)	https://www.epma.com/
GeniCore Sp. Z. o.o. (PL)	https://genicore.eu/
Geo Unterweissacher GmbH (AT)	https://www.geo-unterweissacher.at/
Geologische Bundesanstalt (AT)	https://www.geologie.ac.at/
La Palma Research Centre SL (ES)	https://www.lapalmacentre.eu/
MBN Nanomaterialia Spa (IT)	https://www.mbn.it/
RGS Development BV (NL)	https://www.rgsdevelopment.nl/
Statny Geologicky Ustav Dionyza Stura (SK)	https://www.geology.sk/
Sintef AS (NO)	https://www.sintef.no/
TEGnology ApS (DK)	https://www.tegnology.dk/
Agencia Estatal Consejo Superior De Investigaciones Cientificas (ES)	https://www.csic.es/

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Twitter | LinkedIn | YouTube | Instagram

Figure 17: Screenshot of page “Consortium” of the START website.

5.2.7 Subscribe

It is foreseen that some material can be freely downloadable, but for other materials subscription to the START mailing list will be required. This has the objective of creating a community of interested people, that will give the explicit permission of sending informative communication (thus complying with the requirements of the GDPR regulation).

In the “**Subscribe**” page (Figure 18), the first possibility given is therefore to subscribe to the mailing list; but direct E-Mails of contacts (of the project coordinator and of the leader of WP6 “Dissemination and Communication”) are also shown, and a generic contact form, for communications via web, is also offered.

SUSCRIBE

If you want to be kept informed about the activities in the project by receiving our news, fill the form here:

If you want to contact us, you can send an E-Mail for one of the following contacts:

- Filipe NEVES filipe.neves@lneg.pt
- Bruno VICENZI bv@epma.com

or you can send us a message using the form on the side.

Fields marked with * are required

Name*

Email*

Subject*

Message*

CONTACT US

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Figure 18: Screenshot of page “Subscribe” of the START website.

By clicking the button “Subscribe” the reader is taken to the registrations form (Figure 19), that is linked to the SendinBlue¹ mass mailing software. An E-Mail with the coordinates of the subscriber is then sent to EPMA, that collects the names and E-Mails for the dissemination campaigns. The registrations are so constituting the base for dissemination of info via E-mail, without risking being listed as spammers.

¹ <https://www.sendinblue.com/>

The image shows a registration form for a newsletter. The form is titled "Newsletter" and includes the following elements: a heading "Subscribe to our newsletter and stay updated.", a label "Enter your First Name *", a text input field for "First Name", a small text "Customize this optional help text before publishing your form.", a label "Enter your Last Name *", a text input field for "Last Name", another "Customize this optional help text before publishing your form." text, a label "Enter your email address to subscribe *", a text input field for "EMAIL", a small text "Provide your email address to subscribe. For e.g abc@xyz.com", a checkbox with the text "I agree to receive your newsletters and accept the data privacy statement.", a small text "You may unsubscribe at any time using the link in our newsletter.", a logo for Sendinblue (a blue circle with a white checkmark and stars), and a paragraph of French text: "Nous utilisons Sendinblue en tant que plateforme marketing. En soumettant ce formulaire, vous reconnaissez que les informations que vous allez fournir seront transmises à Sendinblue en sa qualité de processeur de données; et ce conformément à ses conditions générales d'utilisation.", and a dark blue "SUBSCRIBE" button.

Figure 19: Screenshot of the registration form based on SendinBlue.

5.3 FUTURE IMPROVEMENT OF THE WEBSITE

Some features, as mentioned in the previous text, will be introduced as soon as possible to make the website more user friendly, and the first news and documents will be uploaded.

During the course of the project, the website will be continually updated. Other specific pages might be created, at lower levels or at menu levels. For instance, specific pages about organised events could be highlighted (possibly a further menu item “Events” could be added, with several subpages).

All newsletters, news items, documents and videos produced will be either embedded or linked in the relevant pages.

5.4 WEBSITE PERFORMANCE METERING

To analyse the performance of the website and collect data, we will use the **Google Analytics** website. After a starting configuration phase, we will be able to track the visits of our audience.

Google Analytics, a service offered by Google, is by far the most used tool for website traffic analysis².

With Analytics we will meter:

- Audience (users, new users, numbers of sessions per user, pageviews, pages/session)
- Acquisition
- Behaviour (visited pages)

Of course, the website will respect the GDPR EU regulation as explained earlier.

² https://w3techs.com/technologies/overview/traffic_analysis, consulted on 07/07/2022.

6 SOCIAL MEDIA

In the original proposal, the START consortium indicated the following information about the use of **social media** for Dissemination and Communication:

Tool:	Social media
Purpose:	LinkedIn, YouTube and Twitter will be considered as main dissemination channels, Slideshare and Twitch as secondary dissemination channels. LinkedIn supports community management with restricted fora. A YouTube channel will be used to engage with a broader audience by sharing videos, including an introduction to START, short interviews, and selected partner videos.
Audience:	All groups
Due:	M02 onwards
Quantified targets:	Twitter: 1000 followers in year 1, rising to 2500 by the end of the project; LinkedIn: 800 followers by the end of the project.

Social media will be one of the pillars of Dissemination, as their use is nowadays ubiquitous and any dissemination campaign, especially with scientific and industrial targets, must exploit their potential as much as possible. Every social media has different functions as the audience is different. For this reason, START has chosen LinkedIn and Twitter to transmit information, using YouTube, Twitch and SlideShare as repositories of video and written material.

In the following, all social media accounts opened will be discussed.

6.1 LINKEDIN PAGE

LinkedIn (www.linkedin.com), since December 2016 owned by Microsoft, is the most highly rated social media for professionals, as it combines B2B contacts and job market contacts, and boosts networking and career development. It has more than 830 million members in 200 countries and regions as of April 2022 (Figure 20³). More than 216 million are in the Europe and Middle East zone, just below the 230 million for Asian and Pacific and above the 208 million reported for North America. 58 million companies worldwide are listed there.

³ <https://news.linkedin.com/about-us#Statistics> , consulted on 17/06/2022

More than 830 million members in 200 countries and regions worldwide*

*Membership numbers are updated quarterly after Microsoft Earnings. * Numbers reflect InCareer app membership as of December 2021.

Figure 20: LinkedIn membership in April 2022.

Among the consortium, most of the partners have LinkedIn pages and have employees with personal profiles. Figure 21 is a listing of present partner pages with the number of followers and the employee accounts present on LinkedIn. EPMA also owns a group in addition to the company page. As it can be seen, the total number of followers exceeds 130k (clearly with potential multiple counts for the same follower though).

Partner	Acr	Page link	Totals		
			Followers	Employees	Updated
Laboratorio Nacional de Energia e Geologia I.P.	LNEG	https://www.linkedin.com/company/ineti/	1867	95	17/06/2022
3 Drivers - Engenharia, Inovacao e Ambiente Lda	3DRIVERS	https://www.linkedin.com/company/3drivers/	1444	21	17/06/2022
ASOCIACION DE SERVICIOS DE GEOLOGIA Y MINERIA IBEROAMERICANOS	ASGMI	https://www.linkedin.com/company/asgmi/about/	272	3	17/06/2022
BUNDESANSTALT FUER GEOWISSENSCHAFTEN UND ROHSTOFFE	BGR	https://www.linkedin.com/company/bgr-bund/	3017	331	17/06/2022
EUROPEAN POWDER METALLURGY ASSOCIATION AISBL	EPMA	https://www.linkedin.com/company/european-powder-metallurgy-association	4795	13	17/06/2022
European Powder Metallurgy Association Networking Group	EPMA	https://www.linkedin.com/groups/2934690/	3277	-	17/06/2022
GeniCore	GeniCore	https://www.linkedin.com/company/genicore/	296	10	17/06/2022
GEO Unterweissacher GmbH	GEO	https://www.linkedin.com/company/geo-unterweissacher/	49	6	17/06/2022
GEOLOGISCHE BUNDESANSTALT	GBA	https://www.linkedin.com/company/geologische-bundesanstalt/	592	45	17/06/2022
LA PALMA RESEARCH CENTRE SL	LPRC	https://www.linkedin.com/company/la-palma-research-centre-sl/	338	7	17/06/2022
MBN NANOMATERIALIA SPA	MBN	https://www.linkedin.com/company/mbn-nanomaterialia-s.p.a/about/	-	3	17/06/2022
MATRES SCRL	MATRES	-	-	-	17/06/2022
RGS DEVELOPMENT BV	RGS	https://www.linkedin.com/company/rgs-development-b.v./	279	12	17/06/2022
STATNY GEOLOGICKY USTAV DIONYZA STURA	SGUDS	https://www.linkedin.com/company/state-geological-institute-of-dionyz-stur/	126	41	17/06/2022
SINTEF AS	SINTEF	https://www.linkedin.com/company/sintef/	47069	2347	17/06/2022
TEGNOLOGY APS	TEGNOLOGY APS	https://www.linkedin.com/company/tegnology-aps/	330	10	17/06/2022
AGENCIA ESTATAL CONSEJO SUPERIOR DE INVESTIGACIONES CIENTIFICAS	CSIC	https://www.linkedin.com/company/csic/	68307	5015	17/06/2022

Figure 21: START LinkedIn partner pages with the number of followers and the employee accounts present on LinkedIn (on 17/06/2022).

As foreseen, EPMA opened a **START LinkedIn account**. Its link is:

<https://www.linkedin.com/company/start-he-project/>

consistent with the domain name chosen for the website. A screenshot of the page is visible in Figure 22. As can be seen, the branding is consistent with the guidelines and a new picture was prepared as “cover image” by combining the group picture taken at the KoM in Lisbon and some of the available graphic elements.

Figure 22: START LinkedIn page as of 13/07/2022.

On LinkedIn other features could be started, like a LinkedIn group, public or private. This possibility will be discussed later in the project, possibly in view of the Clustering activities or for events, or specific targets.

6.2 YOUTUBE PROFILE

YouTube (www.youtube.com) is an online video sharing and social media platform. It was established in 2005 and was later bought by Google. In January 2022, it ranked⁴ second among social networks with 2.562 billion monthly active users (the first is Facebook with 2.910 billion users). The revenues from advertisement in 2021 amounted to about 29 B\$⁵. Its services include video hosting (with the possibility of embedding the video player in other websites), live streaming, and specific channels for TV, movies, music, kids, etc. Its impact on present culture is huge, as it is nowadays comparable to Google Search itself in terms of access, and as it offers hosting not only for short videos like some other platforms, but also for longer contents. Almost all news channels offer information on YouTube, and many films and documentaries are available on the

⁴ <https://www.statista.com/statistics/272014/global-social-networks-ranked-by-number-of-users/>, consulted on 30/06/2022.

⁵ <https://www.hollywoodreporter.com/business/digital/youtube-ad-revenue-tops-8-6b-beating-netflix-in-the-quarter-1235085391/>, consulted on 30/06/2022.

platform directly from the media companies' channels. It is the obvious choice to store public video materials, which is the case for dissemination of a project, and also for wider communication, as the audience on this platform includes all ages, occupations, nationalities, genders, interests.

According to the plan, EPMA has created a **YouTube profile associated with START**, that is reachable at the following address:

<https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCHVjEhpVz9uaEgzlCj2InPA>

and visible in Figure 23.

Figure 23: START YouTube channel, presently empty, created for the project (status on 05/07/2022).

Some information about the project has been placed in the “About” description (Figure 24).

Figure 24: START YouTube channel, presently empty, created for the project (status on 05/07/2022): the content of the “About” description sheet.

It is planned that YouTube will be used to host all public videos that will be produced during the project. The contents could be later be linked to, but also embedded directly on the project website. This choice will keep the viewer on the website, so that they will be exposed to project news for a longer time while viewing the video, whereas a link would bring them to the YouTube channel, where they will basically be exposed only to the other video contents.

In case, specific playlists to group of videos that have similar contents could be created, in order to propose the viewer a series of videos that can be played together. These can be accessed directly on the channel or linked into other media.

6.3 TWITTER ACCOUNT

Twitter (www.twitter.com) is a social media platform founded in 2006. It is branded as a microblogging and social networking service on which users post and interact with messages known as "tweets". It allows users to post, like and retweet tweets, facilitating a quick avenue for information sharing. Twitter has 217 million users and had a revenue of \$5.08 billion in revenue in 2021⁶. Based on Statista⁷, from the top-20 countries in Twitter users, four are in Europe (United Kingdom, France, Spain, Germany).

Within the START consortium about half of the partners have a Twitter account allowing for a moderate replication of the project tweets (LNEG, ASGMI, EPMA, GBA, LPRC, RGS and SINTEF). Most of the interactions arising from the Twitter posts are expected to come from engagement with followers and relevant accounts to the topics at hand (raw materials, energy, sustainability, etc).

The **START Twitter account**:

https://twitter.com/START_HEproject

was created in July 2022 by LPRC, according to plan. The project page follows the branding guidelines (Figure 25).

⁶ <https://www.omnicoreagency.com/twitter-statistics/>

⁷ <https://www.statista.com/statistics/242606/number-of-active-twitter-users-in-selected-countries/>

Figure 25: START Twitter social media channel page. Main information on the project is included and the page follows the branding guidelines.

In START, Twitter will be used to develop messages primarily targeting business and policymakers. Engagement with users with Twitter starts from the beginning of the project.

6.4 TWITCH PROFILE

Twitch (www.twitch.tv) is a different style of social media when compared to the “traditional” channels also used in START. In fact, Twitch is a video live streaming service focused on transmitting live video game play. The platform started in 2011, today counts 140 million active users with 73% of Twitch users being 35 or less years old⁸.

The START Twitch profile will be mostly used later during the project implementation to showcase the “Serious game” that will be developed as part of WP7 – game runs will be broadcast on the platform, encouraging new players to join in and help the project to gain valuable insights.

The **START Twitch account**:

https://www.twitch.tv/start_he_project

was created in July 2022 by LPRC, according to plan, following the branding guidelines (Figure 26).

⁸ <https://backlinko.com/twitch-users>

Figure 26: START Twitch social media channel page. Main information on the project is included and the page follows the branding guidelines.

6.5 SLIDESHARE ACCOUNT

Slide Share is a presentations and documents sharing platform, now owned by Scribd, focused on professional content.

Users can share content by uploading files privately or publicly in different formats such as PowerPoint, Word, PDF or OpenDocument. Content can be viewed on the site itself or embedded in other sites.

Slide Share works as a social media network so users can share the uploaded files, can rate and comment the content. It is similar to YouTube but for presentations and documents.

SlideShare has more than 80 million users, and over 18 million uploads in 40 content categories. It is one of the top 100 most visited websites in the world.

Public presentations about the objectives and development of the project targeted to general public and other more technical content will be uploaded according to the strategy of Communication Plan. This content can be after shared in other social media as LinkedIn or Twitter by link or embedded in project and partners websites.

This will allow to manage, share, disseminate and preserve information and knowledge about the project efficiently and connect to other related projects.

According to the plan, ASGMI has created a **START Slide Share account** (Figure 27):

<https://es.slideshare.net/StartProject/>

and some information about the project has been placed in the description.

Figure 27: START SlideShare account. Main information on the project is included and the page follows the branding guidelines.

A first document is available, the same that is on the website “Documents” page, again in pdf format.

6.6 SOCIAL MEDIA PERFORMANCE METERING STRATEGIES

The evaluation of the performance of online dissemination will be based on the available metering services intrinsic of each social media.

6.6.1 LinkedIn

We will be using **LinkedIn Analytics**⁹, the intrinsic analytics service offered by the platform, and we will feed some of these data into the **START Excel tool** for monitoring online dissemination (see section 6.6.6).

LinkedIn Analytics is available for LinkedIn pages and gives insight on multiple indicators related to page activities. The available information is organised as follows:

- Visitors
 - Highlights (Page views, Unique visitors, Custom button clicks) values and change rates in the time period chosen
 - Visitor metrics (Page views, Unique visitors) charts in the time period chosen, page by page (Home, About, Insights, People)

⁹ <https://www.linkedin.com/help/linkedin/answer/a547077/linkedin-page-analytics-overview?lang=en>

- Visitor Demographics (by Job Function, Company size, Industry, Location and Seniority)
- Updates
 - Highlights (Reactions, Comments, Shares) values and change rates in the time period chosen
 - Metrics (Impressions, Unique impressions, Clicks, Reactions, Comments, Shares, Engagement rate) charts in the time period chosen, divided between Organic (spontaneous) and Sponsored (paid)
 - Update engagement, with Post type, Audience, Impressions, Views, Clicks, CTR, Reactions, Comments, Shares, Follows, Engagement rate $[(\text{Clicks} + \text{Likes} + \text{Comments} + \text{Shares} + \text{Follows}) / \text{Impressions}]$, post per post
- Followers
 - Highlights (Total followers, New followers) values and change rates in the time period chosen
 - Follower Metrics charts in the time period chosen, divided between Organic (spontaneous) and Sponsored (paid)
 - Follower Demographics (by Job Function, Company size, Industry, Location and Seniority)
 - List of followers
- Competitors (a list of competitor pages must be created, e.g., similar projects)
 - Follower Metrics (Total followers, New followers) in the time period chosen, for each competitor page
 - Organic Content Metrics (Total engagements (Reactions + Comments + Shares), Total posts) in the time period chosen, for each competitor page
- Leads (if forms to collect contacts will be associated to LinkedIn posts)

All this information will be analysed by EPMA throughout the project to monitor the performance on LinkedIn, in order to understand the best way to bring viewers to project information by comparing the effect of different posts and campaigns. Followers and views will be used in the Excel tool mentioned above.

6.6.2 YouTube

We will be using the **intrinsic analytics service** offered by the platform, and we will feed some of these data into the **START Excel tool** for monitoring online dissemination (see section 6.6.6).

In addition to the basic information about the channel (number of subscribers, etc.), the **YouTube Analytics** delivers the following information on Reach, Engagement and Audience:

- Impressions (how many times people have seen an impression, i.e., a picture representative of your videos, on YouTube)
- Impressions Click-Through Rate, or CTR (ratio of clicks to view the videos on impressions)
- Views and unique viewers
- Traffic source (YouTube searches, suggested videos on YouTube, and others)
- Time watched for each video (in hours)
- Average time spent by viewers watching the videos
- Geography by country
- Age and gender

- Subscription status
- Subscription source (where are subscribers arriving from)
- Device type and Playback location
- Subtitles and languages (if used)
- Shares

A sample screenshot of a typical YouTube advanced Analytics page is visible in Figure 28 (not from project's profile, as it would be empty now).

Figure 28: Example of YouTube Analytics (not taken from project's profile).

EPMA will monitor the performance on YouTube by accessing the analytics page regularly, in order to understand the best way to bring viewers to the videos by comparing the effect of different awareness campaigns. Subscribers and views will be used in the Excel tool mentioned above.

6.6.3 Twitter

We will be using the **intrinsic analytics service** offered by the platform, and we will feed some of these data into the **START Excel tool** for monitoring online dissemination (see section 6.6.6).

Twitter registers the account activity and provides a set of statistics that are useful to monitor the impact of the START account. Statistics can be easily seen and exported from the Twitter platform itself, and then integrated into the joint Excel sheet for an overall analysis. These include:

- 1) Impressions
- 2) Engagements
- 3) Engagement rate
- 4) Link clicks
- 5) Retweets
- 6) Replies
- 7) Likes

6.6.4 Twitch

We will be using the **intrinsic analytics service** offered by the platform, and we will feed some of these data into the **START Excel tool** for monitoring online dissemination (see section 6.6.6).

Statistics are provided by the Twitch platform under the Channel Analytics banner. Statistics recorded and provided by the platform include (based on the most relevant statistics to be provided):

- 1) Average viewers
- 2) Live views
- 3) Follows
- 4) Subscriptions
- 5) Time streamed
- 6) Minutes watched
- 7) Max viewers
- 8) Unique viewers

6.6.5 SlideShare

We will be using the **intrinsic analytics service** offered by the platform, and we will feed some of these data into the **START Excel tool** for monitoring online dissemination (see section 6.6.6).

Statistics are provided by the SlideShare platform in the Data Analysis section. Following information are provided by the platform:

- Total views and source of viewers (SlideShare, Google searches, other social media)
- Actions on SlideShare (recommended content, embedded content, comments, downloads and emails)

6.6.6 Monitoring Tool for Online Dissemination

According to previous experiences, an **Excel file will be used to collect the data of dissemination performance on social media**, in order to quantify the audience reached and the interest arisen.

This is located on the START SharePoint (<https://ineg.sharepoint.com/sites/START>) and will contain all the details collected from the different social media posts and contents, and from the website. A preview of the structure of the file is visible in the screenshot of Figure 29.

